

Chemical Engineering Journal 471 (2023) 144534

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2023.144534>

Comment on “Effective sequestration of tetracycline and ciprofloxacin from aqueous solutions by Al-based metal organic framework and reduced graphene oxide immobilized alginate biosorbents”

Khim Hoong Chu ^{*}, Mohd Ali Hashim

Department of Chemical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, University of Malaya, Kuala Lumpur 50603, Malaysia

^{*} Corresponding author.

E-mail address: khimchu@gmail.com (K.H. Chu)

In this letter, we present a critique of the recent paper by Kim et al. [1], which contains interesting data on the adsorption characteristics of tetracycline and ciprofloxacin in both batch and fixed bed systems. Our remarks focus on the modeling results that were obtained by fitting the Bohart–Adams, Thomas, and Yoon–Nelson models to the fixed bed breakthrough data. Previous research [2,3] has shown that the three models are mathematically equivalent, implying that they should yield the same results when applied to a specific dataset. Our comments pertain specifically to the modeling results obtained using the Yoon–Nelson model, but they are relevant to the conclusions drawn from the other two models as well.

In Kim et al.'s article [1], the Yoon–Nelson model is presented in the form of Eq. (1), where c represents the effluent concentration at time t , c_0 denotes the feed concentration, and k and τ are the parameters to be fitted. However, there is a typographical error in Eq. (1). The correct form of the Yoon–Nelson model is provided in Eq. (2).

$$\frac{c}{c_0} = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(kt - k\tau)} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{c}{c_0} = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(k\tau - kt)} \quad (2)$$

One of the four sets of breakthrough data presented in Kim et al.'s study [1] is depicted in Fig. 1, which shows the breakthrough curve of tetracycline at a feed concentration of 5 mg L⁻¹ and flow rate of 0.75 mL min⁻¹. By applying the Yoon–Nelson model to the breakthrough data, Kim et al. obtained the values of $k = 0.0346 \text{ min}^{-1}$ and $\tau = 104.82 \text{ min}$ through a nonlinear regression analysis. The solid line in Fig. 1, taken from the original paper, represents a reasonable fit with an R^2 value of 0.9652. However, when the reported values of k and τ are inserted into Eq. (2), the resulting calculated curve (dashed line) in Fig. 1 contradicts the fitted curve (solid line). According to Eq. (2), the dimensionless effluent concentration c/c_0 should approach one as time increases. Therefore, the fitted curve (solid line) in Fig. 1, which reaches a plateau of around 0.3 at large t , cannot be generated from the Yoon–Nelson model using the reported values of k and τ . It is unclear how this fitted curve was derived.

Fig. 1. Fitting tetracycline breakthrough data with the Yoon–Nelson model. The solid line represents the fitted curve from the original study [1], whereas the dashed line indicates the prediction of Eq. (2), calculated using the reported values of k and τ .

Our attempt to apply Eq. (2) to the breakthrough data is demonstrated in Fig. 2, and it is evident that the fit is exceedingly poor ($R^2 = 0.691$). By extrapolating our fitted curve to higher t values, a sigmoid curve that approaches one can be obtained, as illustrated in Fig. 3. The result in Fig. 3 verifies that the Yoon–Nelson model will predict a breakthrough curve that asymptotes toward one at large values of time.

The four breakthrough curves presented in the original study stabilized at c/c_0 levels of approximately 0.3–0.4, suggesting that the fixed bed could not attain complete saturation. These infinite uptakes of the two antibiotics are incompatible with the notion of physical adsorption, contradicting the maximum adsorption levels observed in the equilibrium isotherm data. Unfortunately, Kim et al. did not provide any explanation for these anomalous breakthrough curves.

Fig. 2. Fitting tetracycline breakthrough data with the Yoon–Nelson model. The solid line represents the fitted curve from Eq. (2).

Fig. 3. Extrapolating the fitted curve in Fig. 2 to higher values of time.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

References

- [1] N. Kim, B. Cha, Y. Yea, L.K. Njaramba, S. Vigneshwaran, S.SD. Elanchezhian, C.M. Park, Effective sequestration of tetracycline and ciprofloxacin from aqueous solutions by Al-based metal organic framework and reduced graphene oxide immobilized alginate biosorbents, *Chem. Eng. J.* 450 (2022) 138068. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2022.138068>.
- [2] R. Apiratikul, K.H. Chu, Improved fixed bed models for correlating asymmetric adsorption breakthrough curves, *J. Water Process Eng.* 40 (2021) 101810. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwpe.2020.101810>.
- [3] K.H. Chu, Fixed bed adsorption of water contaminants: a cautionary guide to simple analytical models and modeling misconceptions, *Sep. Purif. Rev.* 52 (2023) 75–97. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15422119.2022.2039196>.